

STUDIES ON PHOSPHATE FERTILIZERS. PART II. MONOCALCIUM TETRASODIUM PHOSPHATE AND MONOCALCIUM TETRAPOTASSIUM PHOSPHATE

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A product of high phosphate availability is obtained when phosphate-rock is heated with alkali carbonate and hydroxide. An ammonium citrate-soluble phosphate is formed at the melting point of the alkali which does not hydrolyse when leached with water, and conforms to the formula $\text{CaR}_4(\text{PO}_4)_2$, where R is Na or K.

One of the methods of destroying the fluorapatite structure of phosphate rock is heating it at a high temperature alone or with additives. As a result, the citric acid-solubility of the product is increased. Many methods have been suggested but these could not be used owing to the high temperature required and to the electric power not being cheap to commercialise these methods.

Before the last war, considerable work was done in Germany¹ on the decomposition of phosphate rock with sodium carbonate and sodium sulphate. Rhenania phosphate was manufactured by treating crude phosphate with sodium carbonate and silica. Later, in the preparation of Rhenania phosphate, sodium carbonate was replaced by sodium sulphate and potassium sulphate.

Lubec phosphate¹ was produced by burning a mixture of phosphate rock, sodium sulphate and lignite in a reducing atmosphere. The maximum temperature used was 750°-800°. The product obtained was given the formula $2\text{CaO} \cdot 2\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot \text{S}_2$. Agricultural trials on the product proved favourable for its use and pilot plant experiments also proved successful. The process, however, had not been developed on a commercial scale.

Recently, Voiret² fused mineral phosphates with alkali sulphide or with a mixture of alkali sulphate and carbon at 1000° and obtained 75-85% of the total phosphorus pentoxide as available phosphate.

In the present investigation, the reactions of rock phosphate with sodium carbonate and potassium carbonate and with the corresponding hydroxides were studied with a view to gaining insight into the nature of the products formed during these reactions.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The reactions of tricalcium phosphate with alkali carbonates and hydroxides were studied using Makatea phosphate rock containing 84% $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and pure alkalis.

The phosphate rock powder (passing 120 mesh B. S. S.) was mixed thoroughly with the alkali compounds in different proportions. The mixtures with the hydroxides were made by adding requisite quantity of the hydroxide solution to phosphate rock powder and drying on a water-bath, taking care to keep the mixture out of contact with air for preventing the absorption of carbon dioxide. The carbonate mixtures were heated at 900° and hydroxide mixtures between 360° and 500° in an electric furnace for 4 hours. The calcined mass was treated with water and subsequently with neutral ammonium citrate solution. The phosphate content in the water and citrate solutions was determined by the method described in our earlier paper³. The results are shown in Table I. The amount of the alkali was also determined in the water solution in two experiments (Expt. Nos. 5 and 10) by titrating with standard hydrochloric acid solution, using methyl orange as an indicator. The result is shown in the last column in Table I.

TABLE I

Thermal reaction of phosphate rock with alkali carbonates and alkali hydroxides.

Expt. No.	Reaction mixture.	Proportion by wt.	Molar proportion $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$: alkali comp.	Temp.	% Total P_2O_5 .			Remarks.	
					Water soln.	Amm. citrate soln.	Availa- ble.		
1	Rock phosphate alone	1 : 0	1 : 0	400°	Nil	4.98	4.98		
2	Do	1 : 0	1 : 0	900°	„	6.04	6.04		
3	Rock phosphate + $\frac{1}{2}\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3$	1 : 0.25	1 : 0.87	„	„	41.78	41.78		
4	„	1 : 0.5	1 : 1.74	„	4.60	68.96	73.56		
5	„	1 : 0.7	1 : 2.44	„	Nil	56.83	56.83	36.0% alkali in water solution.	
6	„	1 : 1.0	1 : 3.48	„	39.07	30.87	69.94		
7	„	1 : 1.5	1 : 5.22	„	20.20	27.37	47.57		
8	„	+ K_2CO_3	1 : 0.35	1 : 0.94	„	Nil	34.52	34.52	
9	„	„	1 : 0.7	1 : 1.87	„	„	69.29	69.29	
10	„	„	1 : 1.0	1 : 2.67	„	„	74.08	74.08	28.0% alkali in water solution.
11	„	„	1 : 1.4	1 : 3.74	„	1.33	22.03	23.36	
12	„	„	1 : 2.0	1 : 5.35	„	Nil	50.83	50.83	
13	„	+ NaOH	1 : 0.5	1 : 4.61	360°	54.26	7.89	62.15	
14	„	„	1 : 2.0	1 : 18.45	400°	51.88	10.50	62.38	
15	„	+ KOH	1 : 0.72	1 : 4.74	380°	16.94	51.11	68.05	
16	„	„	1 : 1.4	1 : 9.22	500°	13.78	46.80	60.58	

DISCUSSION

The following observations were made in the study of the above reactions.

1. The total P_2O_5 content in the rock phosphate is 38%, which is completely insoluble in water and in ammonium citrate solution. On heating the phosphate rock at 400° and 900° , the ammonium citrate solubility is slightly increased to 4-6%.

2. Both water-soluble phosphate and ammonium citrate-soluble phosphate are formed in the reactions of rock phosphate and alkali carbonates and hydroxides. The water-soluble phosphate, evidently, is trisodium phosphate or tripotassium phosphate formed according to equations (I) and (II), where R is Na or K :

The formation of water-soluble phosphate takes place in the reactions of phosphate rock and sodium carbonate, phosphate rock and sodium hydroxide and phosphate rock and potassium hydroxide, but is almost absent in the reactions of phosphate rock and potassium carbonate. The yield of the water-soluble phosphate was determined by leaching the calcined mass with water. During this process there is, however, a possibility of reversion of the water-soluble phosphate to tricalcium phosphate. Due to this subsequent reversion the results on the yields of water-soluble phosphates were not regular (cf. Expt. Nos. 5 and 7). It has been observed that the formation of R_3PO_4 is favoured when the reaction temperature is well above the melting point of the alkali compound which is evidently due to the accumulation of the alkali in fluid state at some centres giving rise to the formation of the phosphate molecule containing maximum, *i.e.* three, alkali atoms.

3. A part of the alkali is rendered insoluble in water during the extraction, presumably due to the formation of calcium sodium phosphate which is insoluble in water but soluble in ammonium citrate. The amount of this citrate-soluble phosphate proportionately increases with the proportion of the reactant alkali. The optimum molar proportion works out to be $Ca_3(PO_4)_2 : R_2CO_3 :: 1 : 2$ and $Ca_3(PO_4)_2 : ROH :: 1 : 4$, where R is Na or K. The reaction is therefore represented by the equations (III) and (IV).

It is seen that above the optimum proportion, the yield of ammonium citrate-soluble phosphate decreases with increasing proportion of the

reactant (cf. Expt. No. 5, 6, 7, 11, 12). It is probable that under these conditions, water-soluble phosphate is formed in increasing proportion, but owing to reversion, the observed yields are erratic and do not permit drawing definite conclusions.

The formula suggested for the citrate-soluble compound is $\text{CaR}_4(\text{PO}_4)_3$, as it conforms to the optimum proportion for citrate solubility. It is insoluble in water and is not hydrolysed. The mechanism of the reaction can be postulated as follows.

The melting point of sodium carbonate is 851° . At 900° the carbonate melts with decomposition and liberates sodium oxide, which penetrates into the structure of phosphate rock producing monocalcium tetrasodium phosphate.

It may be noted that the formula suggested for Lubeck phosphate, obtained by burning a mixture of phosphate rock, sodium sulphate and lignite, is $\text{CaO} \cdot 2\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot \text{S}_2$. It is probable that sodium sulphide, which is formed by the reduction of sodium sulphate by lignite, is fusible at 900° , and combines with calcium phosphate in the manner suggested above for the interaction of calcium phosphate and sodium oxide.

In a large number of solid reactions (No 6, 7, 8), the reaction actually takes place when one of the reactants or some intermediate compound is in liquid phase at the temperature of the reaction. The present reactions take place at a considerably lower temperature than the melting point of the phosphate of calcium (1670°) or sodium (1340°) or of apatite (1635°). They take place at or above the melting points of the alkali compound which are sodium carbonate (851°), potassium carbonate (891°), sodium hydroxide (318°) and potassium hydroxide (380°).

It may be noted that in the case of alkali hydroxide, almost the same yields are obtained at 360° - 400° , as are realised at 900° with alkali carbonates. These observations establish the fact that the reaction is between tricalcium phosphate solid and sodium oxide in liquid state, which is produced and exists in molten state at 360° - 400° in case of alkali hydroxides and at about 900° in case of alkali carbonates.

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R E F E R E N C E S

1. British Intelligence Objectives Subcommittee Report No. 107, item No. 22.
2. Voiret, *Chem. Abstr.* 1952, No 1721, 643; *Chim. & Ind.*, 1952, 68 191.
3. Mohajir & Datar, *this Journal*, 1955, 10, 13.